

THE EFFECT OF CLASSIC MUSIC THERAPY ON ANXIETY LEVELS OF BREAST CANCER PATIENTS WITH CHEMOTHERAPY RSUD

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Abstract

Introduction: Breast cancer often causes anxiety in patients undergoing chemotherapy due to its prolonged and repetitive process, characterized by mood swings, fatigue, sleep disturbances, and emotional instability. One effective non-pharmacological intervention to reduce anxiety is music therapy, which can help regulate emotions, provide relaxation, and address psychological issues. **Purpose:** This study analyzes the effect of classical music therapy on the anxiety levels of breast cancer patients undergoing chemotherapy at RSUD Tugurejo. **Method:** The type of research used is a quantitative method with a pre-experimental design approach and the research design is a one group pre-post test design. The research instrument used was a questionnaire where the questionnaire was not tested for validity and reliability because these tests had already been carried out. The study population consisted of 48 patients with breast cancer. The analytical test used is the Wilcoxon test. **Result:** The p value = 0.000 was obtained and a negative rank was obtained for 48 respondents, which means that H_0 was rejected and H_a was accepted. This shows that there is an influence of classical music therapy on the anxiety level of breast cancer patients undergoing chemotherapy at Tugurejo Regional Hospital. **Conclusion:** There is an influence between classical music therapy on the anxiety level of breast cancer patients and chemotherapy at Tugurejo District Hospital, with the pre-post test score criteria showing a negative rank as many as 48 respondents experienced a decrease in anxiety, indicated by the p value = 0.000.

Keywords : Music Therapy, Anxiety Levels, Breast Cancer, Chemotherapy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Breast cancer is a disease caused by the presence of malignant tumors in the breast tissue. Breast cancer is a disease that threatens the lives of many women in the world (1). The cause of high mortality due to breast cancer is the detection of cancer at an advanced stage even though at an advanced stage, treatment for breast cancer is very difficult (2). The treatment method that can be used to treat breast cancer is chemotherapy. Chemotherapy is a treatment method that is carried out systemically. The aim of chemotherapy is to inhibit and kill the growth of cancer cells so that they do not spread further ((3). Chemotherapy is a treatment for cancer that is recommended with various considerations and procedures that are actually possible. This has various impacts that the patient must accept. Chemotherapy has a negative impact on the patient's body. One of them is a change in body metabolism which can cause a decrease in appetite. This decrease in appetite results in decreased nutritional intake in the body. The decrease in nutritional intake causes patients to experience a decrease in quality of life (4)

The impact of chemotherapy on patients is divided into three aspects, including the physical aspect. Physical aspects include decreased appetite, changes in sleep patterns, pain and fatigue. The second aspect is the social aspect which includes personal relationships, family relationships, changes in social interactions with the environment, financial burdens, hopes and goals in life. The third aspect is psychological aspects such as depression, deep sadness and anxiety (4). Anxiety is one of the psychological aspects that breast cancer patients have to overcome when undergoing chemotherapy. High levels of anxiety in patients can worsen the patient's condition.

A common problem that breast cancer patients often face during chemotherapy is anxiety. The cause is chemotherapy which sometimes takes a long time and is repeated. So psychological side effects arise such as depression, fatigue and anxiety ((5) Anxiety is a psychological disorder which can usually be characterized by lack of interest and erratic mood, feeling tired quickly, emotional irritability or rejection, disturbed sleep patterns, easily discouraged, aggressive. In breast cancer patients, anxiety arises because they think about the growth and spread of cancer cells throughout the body at a fast pace, uncertainty about treatment, and concerns about the effects of treatment (1).

This anxiety makes patients always feel restless, which can actually hinder treatment. The effects of changes due to chemotherapy, such as changes in physical shape (body image) and decreased quality of life, are other factors that must be faced by breast cancer patients undergoing chemotherapy (6). The impact of anxiety resulting from cancer and chemotherapy can be done by carrying out non-pharmacological management (5). The function of non-pharmacological management is to provide a relaxing effect on the patient. Non-pharmacological treatment of patients can reduce the adverse effects of chemotherapy treatment. There are many non-pharmacological interventions that can be performed on cancer patients to reduce anxiety. one of. Non-pharmacological interventions that can be carried out to reduce patient anxiety include mental health programs, virtual reality, guided imagery, autogenic exercises, progressive muscle training, and music therapy (7). Music therapy is a non-pharmacological treatment method that has the benefit of providing relaxation. Music therapy can be used to control emotions, provide calm, and overcome psychological problems. Classical music therapy is a reference for the research that will be carried out. Music therapy as a non-pharmacological intervention for breast cancer sufferers undergoing chemotherapy. Music as a language of the soul that can influence and also as a medium to overcome the anxiety of breast cancer patients (1).

Based on a preliminary study on March 5 2023 in the Dahlia 1 Chemotherapy Room at Tugurejo Regional Hospital, researchers obtained data namely that the number of breast cancer chemotherapy patients for one month was 48 female respondents with breast cancer who underwent chemotherapy. Results of interviews with four patients feeling restless, anxious, feeling uncomfortable, feeling worried seen from these words. If it is not addressed immediately, anxiety can interfere with the course of the chemotherapy treatment process. According to the patient, when he was diagnosed with cancer, he was never explained about the problems that would occur during cancer treatment and the impact of chemotherapy. Symptoms that arise after chemotherapy include pain, sleep disturbances, nausea and vomiting. This can make patients anxious. This study analyzes the effect of classical music therapy on the anxiety level of breast cancer patients undergoing chemotherapy at Tugurejo Regional Hospital.

Literature Review Cancer Is A Cell That Grows Uncontrollably In The Human Body. One Type Of Dangerous Cancer Is Breast Cancer. Breast Cancer Is Experienced By Many Women. Breast Cancer Is A Dangerous Type Of Disease. Breast Cancer Is A Dangerous Disease Because The Disease Can Generally Be Seen At An Advanced Stage. Where At This Stage, Breast Cancer Is Very Difficult To Treat. Breast Cancer Can Be Treated For A Very Long Time And Costs A Lot Of Money. This Is What Causes Breast Cancer To Become A Big Problem. Chemotherapy Is A Treatment Process That Aims To Inhibit Or Kill Cancer Cells In The Human Body. Chemotherapy Is A Clinical and systematic treatment that is able to stop cell division with a percentage of between 85-100%. However, there are several things that patients must pay attention to When undergoing chemotherapy, these include changes in the physical, psychological and social aspects that the patient will experience. This is why chemotherapy is carried out with various considerations. The psychological impacts that breast cancer patients often face when undergoing chemotherapy include feelings of depression, anxiety, unstable emotions, decreased vitality and feelings of inferiority due to physical changes that occur due to the effects of chemotherapy (body image)(7).

Anxiety is a psychological disorder which can usually be characterized by lack of interest and erratic mood, feeling tired quickly, emotional irritability or rejection, disturbed sleep patterns, easily discouraged, aggressive. Anxiety can occur in breast cancer sufferers. Triggers for anxiety in patients include breast cancer. The higher the stage of cancer, the higher the patient's anxiety level. Another anxiety faced by patients is when they make the decision to undergo chemotherapy. Chemotherapy is an effective treatment for cancer. However, various impacts which are divided into three aspects, namely physiological, psychological and social environmental aspects make patients experience anxiety. Chemotherapy is a treatment process

that aims to inhibit or kill cancer cells in the human body. Chemotherapy is a clinical and systematic treatment that is able to stop cell division with a percentage of between 85-100%. However, there are several things that patients must pay attention to When undergoing chemotherapy, these include changes in the physical, psychological and social aspects that the patient will experience. This is why chemotherapy is carried out with various considerations. The psychological impacts that breast cancer patients often face when undergoing chemotherapy include feelings of depression, anxiety, unstable emotions, decreased vitality and feelings of inferiority due to physical changes that occur due to the effects of chemotherapy (body image) (8) . Anxiety is a psychological disorder which can usually be characterized by lack of interest and erratic mood, feeling tired quickly, emotional irritability or rejection, disturbed sleep patterns, easily discouraged, aggressive. Anxiety can occur in breast cancer sufferers. Triggers for anxiety in patients include breast cancer. The higher the stage of cancer, the higher the patient's anxiety level. Another anxiety faced by patients is when they make the decision to undergo chemotherapy. Chemotherapy is an effective treatment for cancer. However, various impacts which are divided into three aspects, namely physiological, psychological and social environmental aspects make patients experience anxiety. Music therapy can reduce the patient's anxiety level because basically there are psychological, physiological and spiritual dimensions of human factors. Music can have a positive effect because with music, the human brain relaxes and can provide energy. Music intervention can provide patients with an entertaining stimulus that evokes a calming, pleasant sensation accompanied by focusing attention on the music they hear (9)

2. METHODOLOGY

The method used in this research is an experimental method in the form of pre-experimental design. Experimental research is research that requires the researcher to create research conditions according to the researcher's needs. In this study, researchers used a pre-experimental design in the form of a one group pre-post test design. Experimental research aims to see the relationship in one group during the pre-post test. One group of subjects is used as an observation during the pre-test before intervention or treatment is carried out. Furthermore, the research was carried out post-test after being given intervention or treatment classical music therapy for 20 minutes in one session. (10) The population in this study were all breast cancer patients who underwent chemotherapy at Tugurejo Regional Hospital, namely 48 patients in 1 month. The sampling technique used was a total sampling of 48 patients. Total sampling. The Total Sampling technique is a sample taken from all members of the population used as a sample, namely all breast cancer patients undergoing chemotherapy (11).

This research will use the STAI type of instrument. State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI) scale. The STAI scale is an instrument that can be used to measure anxiety (12) Measurements with STAI consist of: 2 indicators with a total of 20 items. The categories include a score of 20-29 indicating normal. A score of 30-39 indicates mild anxiety. A score of 40-49 indicates moderate anxiety. A score of 50-80 indicates severe anxiety. The Wilcoxon test is used to test the difference in the means of two paired samples on ordinal or interval scale data, especially if it is not normally distributed as an alternative to the paired sample t-test. Regression analysis is used to assess the relationship between risk factors (independent variables) and dependent variables, with a significance level (α) of 0.05. If $p < 0.05$, there is a significant influence between the independent and dependent variables, whereas if $p > 0.05$, there is no significant influence. This research has been ethically tested and in accordance with ethical considerations, all respondents were given music therapy and the music therapy provided was safe and did not have a negative impact on patients.

3. RESULT

Table 1. Characteristics based on age, education, Cancer History, Pre-Test Post -Test Anxiety Level of, of the Effect of Classical Music Therapy on of anxious patients with breast cancer undergoing chemotherapy at Tugurejo Regional Hospital, Semarang 2024 n=48

Age	Total	Percentage
Early Age	7	14.50%
Middle Age	7	14.50%
Late Age	34	71%
Total	48	100%
Education	Total	Percentage
Junior high school	9	18.80%
Senior high school	32	66.70%
College	7	14.60%
Total	48	100%
Cancer History	Total	Percentage
1-2 Year	11	22.90%
3-5 Year	29	60.40%
6-10 Year	8	16.70%
Total	48	100%
Anxiety Level (Pre-Test)	Total	Percentage
Mild Anxiety	3	6.30%
Moderate Anxiety	22	45.80%
Severe Anxiety	23	47.90%
Total	48	100%
Anxiety Level (Post-Test)	Total	Percentage
Mild Anxiety	5	10.40%
Moderate Anxiety	30	62.50%
Severe Anxiety	13	27.10%
Total	48	100%

The majority of breast cancer patients undergoing chemotherapy at Tugurejo Regional Hospital, Semarang in 2024 will be in their late age (71%). Meanwhile, patients who are in their early and middle ages each has the same proportion, namely 14.5%. This shows that the majority

of patients with anxiety during chemotherapy are those in the elderly group. The majority of breast cancer patients who experience anxiety during chemotherapy at Tugurejo Hospital Semarang in 2024 have a high school education level (66.7%). A small proportion of respondents have a college education (14.6%), while the other 18.8% had junior high school education. This shows that the majority of patients with anxiety during chemotherapy have a secondary educational background. Most breast cancer patients undergoing chemotherapy at Tugurejo Hospital Semarang in 2024 have a history of cancer for 3-5 years (60.4%). Meanwhile, patients with a history of cancer of 1-2 years amounted to 22.9%, and those with a history of 6-10 years were 16.7%. This shows that the majority of patients have experienced breast cancer in the medium term before undergoing chemotherapy. The majority of breast cancer patients undergoing chemotherapy at Tugurejo Regional Hospital, Semarang in 2024 will experience severe anxiety (47.9%). Almost half of the respondents experienced moderate anxiety (45.8%), while only a few experienced mild anxiety (6.3%). This Matter shows that the majority of patients experience quite high levels of anxiety before undergoing chemotherapy. Most breast cancer patients undergoing chemotherapy at Tugurejo Regional Hospital, Semarang in 2024 experienced mild anxiety (62.5%). Others experienced moderate anxiety (27.1%). while 10.4% of respondents did not experience anxiety (normal). This shows that although anxiety still occurs after the intervention, the majority of patients are at a milder level of anxiety.

Table 2. The Effect of Classical Music Therapy on Anxiety Levels of Breast Cancer Patients with Chemotherapy at Tugurejo Hospital Tugurejo Semarang 2024 n=48

Anxiety Level	Before Intervention		After Intervention		P value
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	
Normal/	0	0%	5	10,4%	0.000
Mild Anxiety	3	6,3%	30	62,5%	
Moderate Anxiety	22	45,8%	13	27,1%	
Severe Anxiety	23	47,9%	0	0%	
Total	48	100%	48	100%	

Classical music therapy has proven effective in reducing anxiety levels in breast cancer patients undergoing chemotherapy at Tugurejo Hospital, Semarang. Before the intervention, most respondents experienced severe anxiety (47.9%), but after being given classical music therapy, severe anxiety was no longer found, and the majority of respondents experienced mild anxiety (62.5%). Apart from that, there were 10.4% of respondents who achieved a normal or anxiety-free condition after therapy.

Table 3. Respondents Based on Pre and Post Test Anxiety Levels of Patients with Breast Cancer Undergoing Chemotherapy at Tugurejo Regional Hospital, Semarang 2024 n=48

		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Post-Test Score Category - Pre-Test Score Category	Negative Rank Positive Ranks Ties	48 ^a 0 ^b 0 ^c	24.50 .00	1176.00 .00
	Total	48		

The results of the Wilcoxon test showed that classical music therapy had a significant effect on reducing the anxiety level of breast cancer patients undergoing chemotherapy at Tugurejo Regional Hospital, Semarang (p-value = 0.000). All patients experienced a decrease in anxiety after intervention, with no one experiencing an increase or remaining at the same level of anxiety. This indicates that classical music therapy can be an effective method in reducing patient anxiety during chemotherapy. In line with research by (13) which explains that a person's level of education can influence cognitive thinking patterns, which are greatly influenced by information

obtained during the education process and experiences experienced throughout life. (14) explained that the level of education is often associated with knowledge, where high school graduates demonstrate a fairly good understanding, including regarding chemotherapy, as well as the ability to share information with other people. Higher education tends to increase more effective utilization of health services and interactions. Women with a high school education have sufficient thinking capacity to make the right decisions and tend to be more aware of the importance of self-examination for breast cancer.

Based on the researchers' assumptions in this study, the level of education influences behavior and increasing knowledge, especially in the health sector. The higher a person's education, the easier it is for them to receive information from outside, which has an impact on increasing knowledge. Apart from that, education also influences a person's ability to receive and manage information, which can then influence behavior, both positive and negative, which has an impact on their health status. muscle tension, and reducing anxiety in chemotherapy patients, thereby reducing the level of anxiety, where after being given music therapy, the anxiety of some respondents decreased to mild anxiety. When patients find out that they have breast cancer, they often face uncomfortable psychological conditions, such as anxiety, confusion, sadness, panic, restlessness, loneliness and even fear of death (15) The long treatment process also often causes anxiety, especially regarding the treatment procedures that will be undertaken and the impacts that may arise. Anxiety itself is an emotional response that involves feelings of uncertainty and worry. Breast cancer patients undergoing chemotherapy often experience high levels of anxiety. This anxiety can be caused by the psychological impact of cancer, disturbances in self-image, and reactions to the treatment process. If not handled properly, this anxiety can affect the patient's quality of life and interfere with the course of treatment (16) Anxiety tends to increase when patients think about changes that will occur in the future regarding their disease condition and the treatment they have to undergo, such as chemotherapy, so it can be concluded that why patients after being given classical music therapy before undergoing chemotherapy experience a decrease in anxiety to mild anxiety, which means that even though the percentage of anxiety is not large, anxiety in patients who will undergo chemotherapy still needs to receive serious attention by the health team. Because this anxiety will affect the patient's recovery process. Anxious conditions will increase the release of renin, angiotensin, aldosterone, and cortisol which causes vasoconstriction of blood vessels so that the blood supply to the heart decreases, causing anxiety to become lighter.

This is supported by researchers (17) who explain that anxiety before chemotherapy often occurs because the patient is unaware of the consequences of chemotherapy and is afraid of the procedure itself. Anxious patients usually experience feelings of fear or anxiety, such as fear of the unknown, for example facing surgery, anesthesia, financial problems, family responsibilities, pain, fear of changes in self-concept, even death. This anxiety can trigger physical and psychological changes. Researchers (18) also explained that as many as 45.4% of patients with breast cancer undergoing chemotherapy experienced anxiety due to physical integrity factors and 48.5% experienced anxiety due to threats to themselves. Threats to oneself that cause anxiety include low self-esteem due to the side effects of chemotherapy as well as changes in roles in the family and environment. Meanwhile, the threat to physical integrity that causes anxiety in cancer patients related to chemotherapy is the physical limitations that arise as a result of the side effects of chemotherapy.

Researchers (10) explain the same thing, namely that a person's emotional response to procedural stress and anxiety can increase suffering and affect a person's recovery. One easy, safe and cheap way to reduce anxiety is through music therapy. Based on the results of researchers in this study, many side effects appeared after breast cancer patients underwent chemotherapy, one of which was anemia. Anemia can reduce the capacity of oxygen transport to the tissues causes the patient to experience activity intolerance. This condition can threaten changes in the patient's role both in the family and in society because in this phase the patient will experience severe anxiety. The Effect of Classical Music Therapy on the Anxiety Level of Breast Cancer Patients with Chemotherapy at Tugurejo Regional Hospital

Based on the results of research conducted on 48 respondents, the analysis showed the influence of classical music therapy on the anxiety level of breast cancer patients and chemotherapy at Tugurejo District Hospital. It was found that 23 respondents (47.9%) experienced a decrease in severe anxiety and 30 respondents (62.5%) decreased to mild anxiety after being given classical music therapy. Researchers assume that classical music therapy is a

non-pharmacological therapy that can be given to individuals with indications of anxiety, where classical music can suppress the sympathetic nervous system which results in a decrease in the body's response to stress. The rhythm of classical music can trigger the brain to release endorphin hormones and help reduce anxiety. It is known that the result of the negative rank or difference (negative) in this study was 48 respondents, which means that service quality for the pretest and posttest was 48, this value of 48 indicates a decrease from the pretest value to the posttest value.

The results of this research are in line with the research of (19) which proves that the results of the analysis obtained the mean value of anxiety before being given music therapy was 23.27 and after being given music therapy the respondents received music intervention treatment 3 times. In 3 consecutive days, the mean was 17.94 with a P value = 0.000 ($P < 0.05$), it can be concluded that there was a significant influence on anxiety levels before and after being given music therapy. This can happen based on listening to music with good harmony which will stimulate the brain to carry out the process of analyzing the song, and through the cochlear nerve the music is captured and transmitted to the brain nerves then the music will influence the pituitary to release beta-endorphin hormones (happiness hormones) or pleasant stimulation causes the release of endorphins in the descending control system which results in less stimulation delivered to the brain and the tones provide stimulation in the form of alpha waves. Researchers (20) also proved the same thing, namely the results of the study showed that providing classical music therapy was able to reduce anxiety levels by 11.62% with a p-value of 0.000 from moderate anxiety to mild anxiety. So it can be concluded that there is an effect of classical music therapy on reducing anxiety levels. This can happen based on music therapy being a therapeutic activity because it is able to improve, maintain and develop mental, physical and emotional health. Classical music with alpha and beta frequencies of 5000-8000 Hz can stimulate the body and mind to relax, thereby stimulating the brain to produce serotonin and endorphin hormones which will have an impact that makes the body relax and makes the heartbeat stable. Increased levels of serotonin become the hormone melatonin regulatory effect on body relaxation so that it can improve mood, whether creating a calm, relaxed, safe or pleasant atmosphere, so as to make the patient feel comfortable.

Researchers (17) proved the same thing, namely that anxiety before intervention was recorded with an average value (mean) of 2.25 and a standard deviation of 0.440. After the intervention, anxiety showed a decrease with an average value of 1.75 and a standard deviation of 0.568. The T test results showed a p value of 0.00 (< 0.05), which means there was a significant difference in the level of anxiety in preoperative patients before and after classical music therapy. This shows that classical music therapy is effective in reducing pre-operative patient anxiety. This can happen because distraction is an effective effort to divert attention that has a positive impact in the short term. One distraction technique used to reduce anxiety is listening to classical music. Based on the researchers' results, the average respondent experienced severe anxiety due to the chemotherapy they were undergoing because of both physical and psychological side effects. Physical side effects in patients with chemotherapy include nausea, vomiting, having grade 0 leukocyte levels and psychologically causing anxiety. Anxiety that is not treated with good management or coping mechanisms can greatly affect the course of treatment or therapy. In breast cancer patients undergoing chemotherapy, anxiety can occur because they stop treatment, which may ultimately decrease their quality of life so that non-pharmacological techniques are needed, one of which is classical music therapy.

Music therapy helps individuals with emotional problems express feelings, improves mood positively and helps in solving problems. Apart from that, music is also used to overcome stress and anxiety. According to (19) the benefits of music include increasing intelligence, refreshing, calm, motivation, as well as therapy for various diseases such as cancer, stroke, dementia, heart disease, pain, learning disorders and as a communication tool. Music not only improves health but can also relieve pain, negative emotions, and reduce anxiety. Music also becomes symbolic for patients, connecting them psychologically with their past and culture. Music therapy works by stimulating the auditory nerve which is then transmitted as vibrations to the brain via the limbic system. In the limbic system, especially in the amygdala and hypothalamus, this stimulus activates the autonomic nervous system, which is closely related to the endocrine system and can reduce hormones related to stress and anxiety. Stimulus also triggers the release of the hormone endorphin, which helps increase feelings of relaxation (21) Music in therapy acts as a facilitator to create a relaxed state, so that the parasympathetic system can function more dominantly. Someone who listens to music becomes calmer and more comfortable, that is very

influential on the level of anxiety. Music therapy is designed to treat various problems and can have different meanings for each individual, so this therapy is used comprehensively to overcome pain, stress management and anxiety ((22) Researchers are limited in collecting data, because the data obtained by researchers is only based on the results of questionnaires filled out by respondents, so conclusions can be drawn only based on data obtained from respondents' questionnaire answers.

4. CONCLUSION

There is an influence between classical music therapy on the anxiety level of breast cancer patients and chemotherapy at Tugurejo Regional Hospital

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REFERENCES

- [1] Beno J, Silen A., Yanti M. Efektivitas Terapi Musik Dalam Menurunkan Tingkat Kecemasan Pada Pasien Kanker Payudara. *Braz Dent J.* 2022;33(1):1–12.
- [2] Kesehatan K, Indonesia R. Rencana kanker nasional 2024-2034. 2024;(September).
- [3] Arisanti JP, Saptarina N, Andarini YD. Evaluasi Penggunaan Obat Kemoterapi Pada Penderita Kanker Payudara Di Rsup Dr. Seoradji Tirtonegoro Periode 2018. *Pharm J Islam Pharm.* 2020;4(2):1.
- [4] Susetyowati S, Pangastuti R, Dwidanarti SR, Wulandari H. Asupan makan, status gizi, dan kualitas hidup pasien kanker payudara di RSUP DR Sardjito Yogyakarta. *J Gizi Klin Indones.* 2018;14(4):146.
- [5] Jelang DW, Kariasa IM, Yona S. Efektivitas Breathing Exercise dalam Menurunkan Kecemasan pada Pasien dengan Kanker Paru. *J Telenursing.* 2024;6(1):1554–62.
- [6] Umam LK, Kusnawan A, Arifin IZ. Bimbingan Rohani Islam dalam Mengurangi Kecemasan Pasien Kemoterapi dengan Spiritual Emotional Technique (SEFT). *Al-Afkar J Islam Studies.* 2024;7(3):1237–52.
- [7] Hermanto A, Sukartini T, Esti Y. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.33846/sf11401> Terapi Non Farmakologis untuk Mengurangi Kecemasan pada Pasien Kanker dengan Kemoterapi: 2020;11(6):334–7. Available from: <https://forikes-ejournal.com/index.php/SF/article/view/sf11401/0>
- [8] 川尻秀一. 「SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals) 持続可能な開発目標」. Vol. 69, *Japanese Journal of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery.* 2023. 409-409 p.
- [9] Nuuru HRA, Pratiwi A. Efektivitas terapi musik sebagai intervensi mengontrol halusinasi pendengaran: case report. *J Keperawatan Jiwa.* 2024;12(2):297–304.
- [10] Fuji Lestari D, Risdiana R. Pengaruh Pemberian Terapi Musik Klasik Terhadap Tingkat Kecemasan Anak Usia Pra Sekolah Saat Di Berikan Terapi Intravena. *J Pendidik dan Konseling.* 2022;4:314–9.
- [11] Sugiono. *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D.* 2023.
- [12] Sulistyarini WD, Suyatmi, Indra Kusuma A, Dwiyantri Abdullah RS, Mia Siska E. Implementasi Intervensi Spritual Guided Imagery (Sgi) Terhadap Kecemasan Pada Pasien Kanker Payudara Yang Menjalani Kemoterapi: Studi Kasus Dan Studi Literatur. *J Ilm Keperawatan (Scientific J Nursing).* 2022;8(2):427–37.

- [13] Prasetyo DY, Suprayitno E. Faktor Kualitas Hidup Pasien Kanker. CareJurnal Ilm Ilmu Kesehatan [Internet]. 2021;9(2):322–33. Available from: <https://jurnal.untri.ac.id/index.php/care>
- [14] Supaati Supaati, Anis Ardiyanti, Nafisatun Nisa. Hubungan Self Efficacy Terhadap Kualitas Hidup Pasien Kanker Payudara. DIAGNOSA J Ilmu Kesehatan dan Keperawatan. 2024;2(3):57–67.
- [15] Aulia F, Ulfah B, Rizqi Agustina Y, Puji Lestari P. Pengalaman Psikologis Pasien Kanker Payudara Dalam Menjalani Kemoterapi. JK J Kesehatan. 2024;2(2):162–71.
- [16] Finna Rachma Agustin, Wita Oktaviana*, Nanda Putri Ariyanti MN. Gambaran kecemasan pada pasien kanker payudara yang sedang menjalani kemoterapi. 2024;12(4):815–22.
- [17] Basri B. Pengaruh Terapi Musik Klasik Terhadap Kecemasan Pasien Pre Operasi Di Instalasi Bedah Pusat Rsup H. Adam Malik Medan Tahun 2018. J Keperawatan Prior. 2019;2(2):41.
- [18] Setyani FAR, P BDB, Milliani CD. Tingkat Kecemasan Pasien Kanker Payudara Yang Mendapatkan Kemoterapi. Carolus J Nurs. 2020;2(2):170–6.
- [19] Fikri M, Fitriani DR. Pengaruh Terapi Musik Terhadap Tingkat Kecemasan Pasien Kanker di Rumah Singgah Kanker Samarinda. Ber Ilmu Keperawatan. 2021;14(1):2.
- [20] Nurhalimah N. The Effect Of Classical Music Therapy On The Anxiety Of Cervical Cancer Patients With Brachytherapy In The Radiation Oncology Service Unit Of Cipto Mangunkusumo Jakarta Hospital. J Kesehatan Pasak Bumi Kalimantan. 2020;3(2):10.
- [21] Jasafat, Ibrahim I, Hatta K. Zikrullah As An Emotional Counseling On Amygdala From Science Approach. J Al-Bayan Media Kaji dan Pengemb Ilmu Dakwah [Internet]. 2020;26(2):250–69. Available from: <https://jurnal.ar-raniry.ac.id/index.php/bayan>
- [22] Lussy Putri Khadijah. Efektivitas Terapi Musik Untuk Menurunkan Tingkat Stres Dan Kecemasan. Detect J Inov Ris Ilmu Kesehatan. 2023;1(3):91–8.